
Master Students' Low Achievement in Writing Dissertations

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Abstract

With the advent of the internet and modern technologies, a variety of information resources have emerged and spread; thereby, the thirst for information has grown and is more urged. Data are becoming more digital; researchers and learners would access easily the wide range of academic resources, which may lead to the attempt of copying an original work or stealing others' thoughts without acknowledging the source. The latter has always been a concern for the academic community and has raised a controversial debate among those searching for new methodologies. It is worth noting that drafting a master memoir in the English language has become a burden on students' shoulders because of several reasons. The act of copying authors' original work is surprisingly noticed in students' final output. To conduct this study, two research instruments have been used; a structured questionnaire handed out to forty-eight (48) students and the analyses of master students' memoirs specialized in Didactics and Literature. The present work portrays a holistic picture of the rationale for such a low achievement in writing a master dissertation. Furthermore, this study aims at analyzing and identifying the students' difficulties that they face when penning the final product and then attempting to find remedial and utilitarian suggestions that would hopefully enhance the students' writing competencies for the ultimate objective of making them avoid falling into the trap of plagiarism.

Keywords: ideas, master dissertations, plagiarism, students, writing

Introduction

To produce a dissertation is a new experience that master students undergo; it is a personal activity performed to show their writing abilities. Yet, these capacities have decreased over the past few years because of some factors, the most important one may be reading absence; hence, students seem uninterested in reading. Additionally, some master students take ready-made works and submit them as their final output; so, the act of stealing someone's intellectual property is plagiarism that is rampant in this era. The latter may occur in writing straightforward projects that students produce and predominantly their master dissertations. Good reading skills are required in written productions. However, teachers have noticed that producing a dissertation has become a burden for students because they have to deploy efforts to select passages and texts to read, think, analyse and produce. This piece of research will shed light on this issue that

is one of the most challenging tasks teachers face while supervising research work with their students.

Thus, the piece of work addresses the following research questions and hypotheses:

- 1) Why has the master dissertation become trivialized by students?
- 2) Why do students find it difficult to achieve a memory?

The hypotheses underlying the above research questions could be:

- 1) Master dissertation seems a burden for students.
- 2) Students rely more and more on either copying or teachers to fulfill their piece of work.

Literature Review

Why Writing a Dissertation

A dissertation is a written task scattered into chapters that students should achieve to show their writing capacities. It generally includes research questions using tools to answer these questions. "A dissertation is a structured piece of writing. It is generally a response to a thesis, (a question or a topic) and develops a logical argument about that thesis."¹ "A dissertation tests your ability to carry out independent research."² "A dissertation demonstrates that a student is capable of identifying his/her area of interest; able to explore a subject in depth; manage a research project; define a suitable question, and use the appropriate research tools."³ Writing a dissertation is a means to improve students' reading and writing skills for it allows them to express themselves. Furthermore, the dissertation project helps them build and enlarge their knowledge in different topics and areas of interest; as a consequence, they get trained in writing.

How To Write a Dissertation

As it was mentioned above, a good piece of research should be structured i.e. it generally covers an abstract, a general introduction, four chapters each of which has to contain an introduction and a conclusion, and a general conclusion. This academic achievement should be realized with students' own analytical and critical thinking and skills. The first part to be considered is the abstract where the reader's attention is incited. The abstract sheds light on the main points of the thesis including the thesis statement, research tools and methods, findings and conclusion. The aim is to get a good and clear idea of what the thesis is about.

The following step, the introduction. The latter covers the different parts of the thesis i.e. a background of the thesis should be given stating the scope. It is also relevant to mention the research questions and the underlying hypotheses narrowing down the theme to make the topic well-defined and clarify the problem. The research questions are answered in the empirical part. The theme in question has to be stated with a clear

¹ Writepass.com/journal/2013/03/what-is-a-dissertation-and-why-is-it-important-2/

² Writepass.com/journal/2013/03/what-is-a-dissertation-and-why-is-it-important-2/

³ Writepass.com/journal/2013/03/what-is-a-dissertation-and-why-is-it-important-2/

objective of the research to convince the reader and urge his interest. The following chapter is chapter one where the subject is described and some definitions of some concepts are presented.

Moreover, chapter two or as it is commonly known, literature review follows. This section includes previous researches related to the theme tackled to facilitate data analysis and discussion in the third chapter. Nevertheless, what is noticed while undertaking research, students may copy from others' works without crediting regardless of the chosen topic. This may be done inadvertently, but definitely may generate plagiarized work. "Direct plagiarism is the most obvious form of plagiarism. This means taking someone else's ideas or work and claiming it as your own without citation." (Shane, 2018, §1) Besides, as Kolin points out "Ethical writing is clear, accurate, fair and honest." (2013, p. 29)

Teachers are confronted with this issue while supervising their students for they meet difficulties to correct them and guide them knowing that the work they are carrying out is not theirs. Being accustomed to such practices, (they get used to taking everything ready from the internet to achieve their projects without deploying efforts to taste their own success.)

Students increasingly abandon reading as long as they have ready-made material, the only task they have to accomplish is to simply rewrite or copy. In that respect, Habibzadeh & Vessal claim that "No doubt plagiarism of ideas is a blatant act of misconduct. Plagiarism of text and recycling of words is also a serious fault in humanities and literature where the essence of work and novelty are wordings and eloquence of the text." (2007, p. 641)

The next chapter is the third one where students will have to display their performed work with the research tools like questionnaires, interviews and class observation. This empirical part covers what students have undertaken with the relevant method. They have to demonstrate how they collected data, how they interpreted it, present deficiencies, explain the strong points and whether they could answer the research questions and confirm hypotheses and what conclusions they reached.

Reasons Related to Low Students' Achievement

Students struggle to start writing their academic piece of work due to:

- The overuse of technological tools.
- The large array of readings they have to achieve.
- Misuse of quotes, i.e. some students overuse quotes, or simply rewrite what the author, has already written in a form of summaries.
- Inability to paraphrase or write in one's own words with crediting; therefore, incapacity to develop critical and thinking skills.
- Fear of error-making.
- Fear of not finishing the work on time because of poor time management.
- Being used to take ready-made work from the Internet.
- Misunderstanding of methodology rules and conceptions.

Accordingly, what was mentioned above, results in poorly written productions including plagiarized passages or sometimes even chapters.

Methods and Materials

Aim of the Study

The rationale aim for undertaking such a study is to help learners develop writing strategies that better enable them to avoid plagiarism. Students are enjoined to compose a master dissertation as a final product of five years of learning the English language. Students are urged to write purposeful memoirs in different disciplines to graduate and start a new career; however, teachers are faced with the issue of students' plagiarism as it is done for various reasons.

Participants

A sample of forty-eight (48) University (master) students was chosen randomly and took part in this case study; and who were enrolled in the Department of English Language and Literature of Dr Moulay Tahar University in Saida during the academic year 2019-2020.

Research instruments

To test the above hypotheses and construct triangulation, the investigators have employed two different research instruments. The researchers provided a structured questionnaire to master students of two groups; one group is specialized in Didactics and the other one is in Literature. In addition to observing master two students' dissertations, the researchers analyzed the way the learners write their memoirs. This is done for the ultimate purpose of gathering thorough data about literary theft. Students' structured questionnaires and exploring their master dissertations are two designed instruments for the sake of evaluating students' competence in writing their final product. The overarching purpose of employing a structured questionnaire as a research tool is that it is strongly believed among scholars that it is a suitable and convenient means for collecting sufficient data in a short period about students' perceptions, attitudes and behaviour towards writing and literary theft.

Research Procedures

Data collected from students' questionnaires and analysis of their memoirs were then analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively.

Results

Analysis of Students' Questionnaire

Question 1: while undertaking a master dissertation, you:

Table1. *Students' strategies while undertaking their master dissertations*

Options	Students
Read various sources first	34
Consult people of the field first	08
Write notes first	01
Design an outline first	05

The table above indicates that the overwhelming number of students; that is around thirty-four (34) out of forty-eight (48) claimed reading first various resources before starting work on their final product, as opposed to eight (8) out of forty-eight (48) informants who reported that they consult first people who are specialized in the field of interest. Further, only one (1) student stated that s/he takes notes while reading and only five (5) questioned students design an outline before commencing their research.

Students were asked to justify their answers. So, some of their responses are summarized in the following claims:

- “I cannot start doing anything related to the dissertation unless I contact people of the field first so that I can have an idea of the methodology”.
- “I read various resources first to collect information about the topic”.
- “Because having an outline and a plan of your entire work will make it easier, also it will help in the data collection process”.
- “It’s always a beneficial step to seek direction and that’s why students consult teachers about the whole process of writing a research paper or other questions”.
- “To lighten your mind and have an idea about what you are going to tackle. Then can write notes about it after that you will be able to design an outline.”

Question 2: you deal with data found in books, articles or the internet with:

Figure 1. Students' use of writing strategies

The graph above reveals that forty-four (44) out of forty-eight (48) questioned students claimed that they paraphrase information found in books, articles or the internet. On the other hand, 8% of the informants which represents only four (4) students out of forty-eight (48) presumed that they use summarizing when dealing with found data. It is worth noting that these two strategies are exceedingly basic in writing a research paper.

Question 3: referencing is:

Table 2. Students' respect of referencing

Options	Students
Always respected	35
Sometimes respected	13
Never respected	00

The table above shows that the majority of the questioned informants, around thirty-five (35) reported that they always respect referencing and give credit for data found in books, articles or the internet. Whereas, only thirteen (13) out of forty-eight (48) stated that referencing is sometimes respected. Surprisingly, no student claimed that s/he never acknowledges the source. It is of great importance on the researchers' part to always cite the sources.

Question 4: a reliable memoire should be a personal product however, some students plagiarize because of:

Figure 2. Students' causes of plagiarism

The informants provided various answers regarding the reasons behind students' plagiarism. 24% of the learners which represents twelve (12) out of forty-eight (48) participants reported that sometimes some students plagiarize because of the lack of analytical skills. 21%, which is around ten (10) out of forty-eight (48) questioned students indicated that they are incapable of paraphrasing; and that makes them fall into the trap of plagiarism. Further, 23% of the participants, which is approximately thirty-four (34) students mentioned that some learners use copy-paste for the ultimate reason of time constraints. On the other hand, seven (7) out of forty-eight (48) informants (15%) claimed that some master students plagiarize because of laziness. More importantly, eight (8) out of forty-eight (48) respondents revealed that some students would plagiarize whether because of the lack of analytical skills and the inability of paraphrasing or because of time constraints and laziness.

Question 5: what do you advise your peers who attempt to plagiarize while achieving a memoire to gain self-satisfaction at the end of their work?

They questioned students offered different and valuable pieces of advice. Their opinions could be summarized in the following claims:

- “to not plagiarize to have a good product and do something great at the end of the studies”.
- “Don't plagiarize and paraphrase the data, learn paraphrasing skills and use your style in writing”.

- They have to do more practice and also to apply his/her style, think about its punishment. They should read a lot to find themselves able to reform their data.”
- “I advise first by starting undertaking the memoire as soon as possible. Second, it is important to gain some analytical skills and learn how to paraphrase. Achieving writing skills will help master dissertation writers to write a neat and personalized work that is out of plagiarism.”

Scrutinizing some Students' Master Dissertations

Passing off others' intellectual properties has always been regarded as unethical and a serious issue amongst scholars and researchers. Nevertheless, university tutors often complain about plagiarized dissertations and consider literary theft as a dishonest act in the academic setting. Students commit plagiarism due to a considerable number of reasons such as:

- The insufficient practice of both writing and reading; the inability of paraphrasing and summarizing.
- Lack of experience since learners are not practically trained on how to pen proposals, and writing a master dissertation is their first try. In other words, they do not have prior knowledge about how to write.
- The advent of technology and easy access to the Internet facilitate plagiarism intentionally or unintentionally.
- Restricted time and laziness on the students' part.

Since literary theft has markedly increased among students researchers, as teachers we investigated the reasons that drive our students towards copy-paste without giving credit to the original work. Additionally, the teacher-researchers explored some students' productions for diagnosing different types of plagiarism and comparing the results with those of the questionnaire. The following extract affirms that this student has mentioned the author and the year of publication, but has forgotten to cite the book's page, the article or a doctoral dissertation. Notably, s/he did not know how to paraphrase the author's words which makes the passage falls under the umbrella of plagiarism.

Abdolmohammadi and Baker (2007) consider that students are delimiting the chances they have to reach upper degrees of mental studying and are also impeding their capacity to derive meaning from texts they are exposed to, when they inadvertently or deliberately present other's authentic works as their own one, this point of view sheds light on various considerations, because when students plagiarise they are likely to hinder themselves from profiting from their study experience...⁴

⁴ B, N. (2019) Reasons behind plagiarism in Master Dissertations. Unpublished Master Dissertations. Saida University. (P, 16).

The researcher raised another piece of work from a different dissertation. It reveals that the student has plagiarized, i.e. the learner did not give credit to the original work. To put it differently, she has neither mentioned the author, the year of publication nor how to paraphrase. Thereby, it is exceedingly difficult to trace the student's work. These instances display students' literary theft and show how learners pass off information consciously or unconsciously.

In addition, language has to do with sounds, symbols, and gestures that a network puts and associates to communicate. On a deeper level, language is an expression of who we are as persons, groups, and nations. Culture refers to a dynamic social system and shared patterns of behavior, ideas, knowledge, attitudes, and values. Also, culture offers the surroundings in which language expand, even as it affects how they are used and interpreted. For instance, a 'good day' in many European cultures is a sunny day, while in many African cultures a 'good day' is a rainy day.⁵

Discussion

This part interprets the results obtained from the students' questionnaire.

In question one, the informants asserted that while undertaking a master dissertation, they would read first different resources for the prime objectives of knowing more about the topic and obtaining sufficient data. Doing this entails a profound reading, and requires the use of some strategies as note-taking, paraphrasing and summarizing.

When asked about dealing with found information in books, articles or the internet, the sweeping majority of the students affirmed that they tremendously depend on paraphrasing when writing down data. Paraphrasing is regarded as one of the basic strategies for the student's learning process as well as for researchers. Paraphrasing is an essential technique that deeply helps researchers avoid plagiarism.

More importantly, it needs primarily reading comprehension, which would enable the students to restate the original work using their structure of sentences via keeping a clear and lucid meaning of the same piece of work with acknowledging the source. In this regard, Darr (2019, p. 17) points out that "...proper paraphrasing helps students avoid accidental plagiarism".

It is worth mentioning that when reading students' master dissertations as examiners or supervisors, the lack and the misuse of both paraphrasing and summarizing are widely noticed. Hence, students should be given sufficient time for writing their final products, and they must be well equipped with techniques and skills that would enable the learners to draft their piece of work properly.

Dealing with referencing in question three, approximately all the informants indicated that they always respect and give credit to the source. The obtained results do

⁵ A, S. (2019) Target language pragmatics in content based oral classrooms. Unpublished Master Dissertation. Saida University. (P. 9)

not equal that of students' master dissertations because most of the students do sometimes acknowledge the original work. However, some other students cite neither the author nor the year of publication and the page number; simply because they do not give close attention to referencing, or because they claim that the information is theirs. Thereby, it is the role of the teacher-supervisor to remind the student about the adequate acknowledgement; otherwise, it is a literary theft or plagiarized data.

Thus, good referencing helps the audience trace the original ideas and reinforces the research's credibility and validity. In this vein, (Santini, 2018) argued that referencing refers to providing close attention to details such as page numbering, the spelling of the author's name and the accuracy of data. Such attention makes a better researcher and develops a good reputation among editors, readers and reviewers. He added that a reader might interpret poor citation as a mark of laziness, inadequate thinking and inappropriate writing (p.2).

When asked about the reasons that are behind students' plagiarism in question four, the informants gave different answers, which varied between the lack of analytical skills, the inability of paraphrasing, time constraints and laziness. Others claimed that some students commit literary theft due to both the lack of analytical skills and the inability of paraphrasing or because of the limited time and laziness. It is essential to mention that in question two (2) all students reported that they employ paraphrasing and summarizing as strategies when dealing with writing down information. Thereby, the obtained results of question four (4) do not equal that of question two (2) in which all the questioned learners reported that they use both paraphrasing and summarizing.

Some students plagiarize simply because they do not work on their dissertations at the very beginning of the academic year; however, they commence collecting data by the mid of the year. Those students find themselves restricted by time and this leads them to literary theft. The use of summarizing and paraphrasing as strategies for drafting a master dissertation require analytical skills, thorough reading and sufficient time, but the vast majority do not have the knack to write adequately their final written productions. The lack of analytical skills and the inability of paraphrasing is markedly shown in master students' dissertations.

Pedagogical Implications

Some Points to Prevent Plagiarism

It is worth noting that students have first to learn methodology rules and conceptions as they should be, then, display motivation and competitiveness to do the best in producing personal work with a wide range of classics during their readings. Nancy Brooks and Abshier House recommended the following:

- Keep track of all sources you use when researching a project,
- If you quote something word-for-word, put quotation marks around what you've copied,
- If in doubt, insert the citation,

- If you are using an idea or concept, you don't need quotation marks, but you still give credit even for a conversation.

Similarly, students are required to use paraphrasing, i.e. read and rewrite in their own words avoiding verbatim plagiarism which exceeds two words, they otherwise have to use quotation marks. One of the most important points is *referencing*, it must be included at the end of the research paper referring back to the works cited.

Conclusion

Writing any scientific work is often challenging for researchers because it necessitates thinking and analysis. It also requires giving credit to the authors' ideas and thoughts for the overarching aim of reinforcing credibility and validity to the research. Referencing is viewed as a prominent aspect that cannot be disregarded in academic writing. Drafting a Master dissertation has always been a complex task for students because of the absence of reading and lack of practising writing. Therefore, students fall into the trap of plagiarism. Researchers ought to acknowledge the resources to appreciate the writer's work in the academic field as well as to facilitate tracing the information for readers.

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Appendices

Appendix 1

Students' Questionnaire

Dear students, you are kindly requested to answer frankly the following questionnaire.
Tick the right answer.

A memoir or a master dissertation is the final product of a five-year learning process which should be an enjoyable performance.

- 1) While undertaking this task you:
- | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| a) Read various sources first | b) consult people of the field first |
| c)write notes first | d) design an outline first |

Justify.....
.....
.....
.....

- 2) You deal with data found in books, articles or the internet with:
- | | |
|----------------|-----------------|
| a) Summarizing | b) paraphrasing |
|----------------|-----------------|
- 3) Referencing is:
- | | | |
|---------------------|------------------------|--------------------|
| a) Always respected | b) sometimes respected | c) never respected |
|---------------------|------------------------|--------------------|
- 4) A reliable memoire should be a personal product however, some students plagiarize because of:
- | | |
|------------------------------|------------------------------|
| a) Lack of analytical skills | b) inability of paraphrasing |
| c) time constraints | d) simply laziness |

5) What do you advise your peers who attempt to plagiarize while achieving a memoire to gain self-satisfaction at the end of their work?
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THANKS FOR YOUR COLLABORATION